

Energy Measures

Tailored measures supporting energy vulnerable households

D6.5

Communication activity report

 <http://www.energymeasures.eu>

 [@NRGMeasures](https://twitter.com/NRGMeasures)

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Author(s)	Michael Anranter		
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	BE		
	PL		
	MK		
	BG		
	UK		
	AT		

Project Coordinator:

Dr Niall Dunphy, Director, Cleaner Production Promotion Unit, University College Cork, Ireland
 T: +353 21 490 1969 | e: n.dunphy@ucc.ie | w: www.ucc.ie/cppu

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About EnergyMeasures

EnergyMEASURES is working to address energy poverty in seven European countries, namely: Belgium, Bulgaria, Ireland, Netherlands, North Macedonia, Poland and the United Kingdom. The project comprises two complementary and synergistic strands of work.

The first strand involves working with energy poor households to improve their energy efficiency through a combination of low-cost measures, and changes in energy-related behaviours and practices. Recruited householders will be provided with low-cost energy measures and empowered to change their energy-related behaviours and practices through an approach that takes account of existing housing conditions and is reflective of their lived experience.

The second strand comprises working with municipalities, energy authorities, housing associations and other relevant actors to assess how current multi-level institutional contexts affect efforts to alleviate energy vulnerability in the participating countries. This knowledge will be used to develop and support the implementation of policy and practice measures which will address structural issues that combine to trap households in energy poverty.

Through this work the project contributes to reducing participants' vulnerability to energy poverty, while at the same time cutting household energy consumption and associated GHG emissions.

For more information see <http://www.energymeasures.eu>

Description of the deliverable and its purpose

This deliverable is a report on all communication and dissemination activities carried out as part of the EnergyMeasures project. This deliverable, which should be read as a complement to deliverables D.6.6 'Main Communication and Dissemination Materials - Part 1' and D.6.7 'Main Communication and Dissemination Materials - Part 2', focuses on the implementation of the communication and dissemination activities over the duration of the project in relation to the key performance indicators defined for project communication and dissemination.

Glossary

D/Del.	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
FB	Facebook
EU	European Union
OA	Open Access
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
WP	Work Package
OKP	Oikoplus GmbH
UCC	University College Cork

1 Communication and Dissemination Background

The objectives of the Work Package 6 as well as the essential steps to achieve these objectives were specified in the DoA:

“The objective of this work package is to maximise the impact of EnergyMEASURES, by achieving the maximum awareness of the project and its results among stakeholders in fuel poverty and consumer behaviour change, and disseminating the best practice methods for engagement of energy poor citizens developed during the project. The WP includes two main areas of work:

- *Communications plan to ensure the widest possible awareness of the project its outputs;*
- *Dissemination strategy to ensure the outputs and lessons from the project contribute to change in policy and practices in tackling energy poverty.” (DoA, p.25)*

Based on the DoA, OIKOPLUS, together with the coordinator, developed two strategy papers to guide communication over the duration of the project. While D.6.2 'Communication Plan' deals with the narrative of communication and the challenges in communication, as well as with internal project communication, the focus of D.6.3 'Dissemination Strategy' was on publicising the tools and approaches developed within the framework of EnergyMeasures.

All three documents provide information about the key performance indicators. They should ensure that the results from the project can be found and utilised by third parties but are also accessible in simple and understandable language. An overview of the key performance indicators, which also form the basis for this report, can be found in Table 1 'KPIs for Communication and Dissemination activities'.

Method	Stakeholder Group	Indicated KPI	Status (as of 16/02/24)
Project Website	All stakeholders	5,000 website visits	6,783 website visits
Local and project-wide press-releases	All stakeholders	10 press releases	5 project-wide; and 3 local press releases; multiple social media announcements
Popular publications (News articles, Blog entries)	All stakeholders	2 publications	6 publications; in addition to 42 popular publications /blogposts published on the EnergyMeasures project website.
Social media, e.g. Twitter, FB, Instagram	All stakeholders	600 followers	594 followers on Twitter, FB, Instagram
Newsletter	All stakeholders	500 readers	1,464 recipients
Project workshops and seminars	Energy poverty practitioners	200 attendees cumulative	917 attendees cumulative plus 386 attendees at training workshops
Paper presentations at scientific conferences	Academics and researchers	10 presentations at conferences	2 conference panels convened; 7 conference

Method	Stakeholder Group	Indicated KPI	Status (as of 16/02/24)
			presentations; 3 guest lectures at universities
OA publications in peer-reviewed journals	Academics and researchers	5 manuscripts	4 Open access publications; 1 edited volume
Cross-participation in events	Cognate projects	10 events (with at least 4 different projects)	10 events (with 8 different projects)
Joint events and initiatives	Cognate projects	3 joint events (with at least 3 different projects)	4 joint events (with 5 different projects)
Participation in activities of key platforms e.g. Engager Cost Action, EPAH	European Platforms	2 events	6 events
National Policy Briefings	Policy makers & EU institutions	7+30 attendees	10 events; 428 attendees
Final project workshop	Policy makers & EU institutions	50 attendees	33 registrations, 17 attendees, 22 views online.

2 Methodology

The basis for the report is a Google Spreadsheet shared within the consortium. All project partners were repeatedly invited to document their own local communication and dissemination measures in order to create the most comprehensive reporting possible. The activities documented by the partners are supplemented by the content and formats curated and organised by OIKOPLUS centrally and on behalf of the project for communication and dissemination. The partner institutions are responsible for the information at local level.

3 Communication and Dissemination Activities

3.1 Project website

Method	Stakeholder Group	Indicated KPI	Status (as of 16/02/24)
Project Website	All stakeholders	5,000 website visits	6,783 website visits ¹

¹ As the click figures for the EnergyMeasures homepage were only strategically recorded from 1 January 2023, the figure shown here is an extrapolation. The extrapolation was based on the number of hits on the homepage since 1 January 2023 (2,035 hits in total)

The [EnergyMeasures website](#) was rolled out in November 2020 and contains several sections. In addition to the project homepage in English, a total of eight landing pages were created in five different languages. All landing pages contain information about local participation in the project:

- Polish: [Projekt EnergyMeasures: pomoc gospodarstwom domowym zagrożonym ubóstwem energetycznym w Bielsku-Białej - EnergyMeasures](#)
- Bulgarian: [Проект EnergyMeasures: подпомагане на домакинствата в риск от енергийна бедност в градовете Габрово и Бургас - EnergyMeasures](#)
- Dutch: [EnergyMeasures helpt! - EnergyMeasures](#)
- North Macedonian: [Проектот EnergyMeasures им помага на енергетски ранливите домаќинства во Македонија - EnergyMeasures](#)
- Flemish: [EnergyMeasures helpt huishoudens met energieproblemen in de regio Turnhout. - EnergyMeasures](#)

3.2 Local and project-wide press releases

Method	Stakeholder Group	Indicated KPI	Status (as of 16/02/24)
Local and project-wide press-releases	All stakeholders	10 press releases	5 project-wide; and 3 local press releases; multiple social media announcements

A total of eight press releases were published during the course of the project. Five of the press releases listed were written by OIKOPLUS and are still available on the homepage.

- EU Project to Combat Energy Poverty - Electricity and Heating May Not Become a Luxury: [EnergyMeasures-Project-Launch-EN.pdf](#)
- Step-by-Step Guidelines: <https://energymeasures.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/09/20230901-Step-by-Step-Guidelines.pdf>
- Book Release <https://energymeasures.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/09/20230913-Book-Release.pdf>
- Final Conference: <https://energymeasures.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/01/Brussels-Event.pdf>
- Project End – Final press release following the conclusion of the project.

Three more press releases were shared by Gemeente Eindhoven/Duneworks/Het PON & Telos, Stowarzyszenie Gmin Polska Sieć Energie Cités, and SAAMO/Kamp C to advertise the official start of the project and the recruitment action in the Netherlands, Poland, and Belgium.

In addition to the press releases, all partners were extremely active in promoting the project. Project content was published in local print and online magazines and newspapers (e.g. Magazyn Samorządowy, Nuachtlitir - Comharchumann Forbartha Mhúscraí, VRT news, Am Paipear, Medium, Groot Eindhoven – see ch.3.3 Popular Publications), on the blogs and microblogs of influencers in the energy sector (e.g. Energietechnologie Thomas More, Energia na miarę, Eco Energy newsletters), as well as on numerous websites of municipalities and local energy consultants associated with the project.

While the self-imposed target of ten press releases was missed, numerous direct initiatives were launched to ensure a regular presence in a wide range of countries and regions.

3.3 Popular publications (News articles, blog entries)

Method	Stakeholder Group	Indicated KPI	Status (as of 16/02/24)
Popular publications (News articles, Blog entries)	All stakeholders	2 publications	6 publications; in addition to 42 popular publications /blogposts published on the EnergyMeasures project website.

Until 14 February 2023, citizens were able to find out more about the EnergyMeasures project in six different publications. Particularly noteworthy among the publications are the interview with J. Claus published on Medium.com (see <https://bit.ly/49TZH1e>), as well as the articles in Magazyn Samorządowy, and Nuachtlitir - Comharchumann Forbartha Mhúscraí.

In addition to the publications in the media, OIKOPLUS has published a total of 42 blog posts, partly in collaboration with the partners. They highlight various aspects of the project work, the tasks and competences of the partner institutions, as well as the results of the project. A list of the titles (hyperlinked) in reverse chronological order can be found in the following table.

1	Illuminating Perspectives: Panel Discussion on Tackling Energy Poverty - EnergyMeasures
2	EnergyMeasures puts on the final spurt - EnergyMeasures
3	A Serious Game on Energy Efficiency - EnergyMeasures
4	The possibilities of an island - EnergyMeasures
5	Energy Measures and its peer projects - EnergyMeasures
6	How complex is it to come up with a universal definition of energy poverty? - EnergyMeasures
7	How the Primary Energy Factor is linked to Energy Poverty - EnergyMeasures
8	Are small initiatives the right force to reduce energy poverty? - EnergyMeasures
9	Reportage from Bielsko Biała - EnergyMeasures
10	Just Transition Commission visits Tighean Innse Gall to find out about EnergyMeasures project. - EnergyMeasures
11	Book in the Making – Living with Energy Poverty: Perspectives from the Global North and South - EnergyMeasures
12	Joining forces to tackle fuel poverty in Ireland - EnergyMeasures

13	EnergyMeasures in Poland: “What we strive for is for citizens to be able to autonomously have a grasp on their energy activity” - EnergyMeasures
14	Country Update: North Macedonia - EnergyMeasures
15	Country Update: Bulgaria - EnergyMeasures
16	Country Update: Netherlands - EnergyMeasures
17	Tackling Energy Poverty through Local Community Engagement – Inspiring Practices from the EnergyMeasures Project - EnergyMeasures
18	Partner Profile: Oikoplus GmbH - EnergyMeasures
19	Country Update: Poland - EnergyMeasures
20	Country Update: Ireland - EnergyMeasures
21	Country Update: Belgium - EnergyMeasures
22	A Chain-Reaction of Negative Consequences of Living in Energy Poverty - EnergyMeasures
23	Sometimes, Energy Poverty is a Hidden Problem - EnergyMeasures
24	The energy crisis in Europe: current insights - EnergyMeasures
25	EnergyMeasures explained - EnergyMeasures
26	EnergyMeasures in Eindhoven - EnergyMeasures
27	Tips and tricks on keeping your home warm this winter, while saving on energy bills - EnergyMeasures
28	Video on Energy Vulnerability (in Dutch) - EnergyMeasures
29	The EnergyMeasures Newsletter #01 - EnergyMeasures
30	How the City of Eindhoven helps energy-vulnerable households in the energy transition - EnergyMeasures
31	Energy poverty in Austria: insights into recent developments. - EnergyMeasures
32	Energy poverty in Poland - Patrycja Płonka gives insights into the support of energy poor households. - EnergyMeasures
33	COOLING TIPS that will keep you and your apartment cool during the summer, while helping you save money - EnergyMeasures
34	Do you speak Energy? What you need to know about energy: a glossary. - EnergyMeasures

35	"I feel a bit frustrated when I feel like people aren't tackling energy poverty because they're waiting for it to be defined." - EnergyMeasures
36	Support for energy-poor households - Dorina Pagliaro gives insights into the situation in Belgium. - EnergyMeasures
37	Energy for All: Lessons learned from the Energie voor Iedereen project taking place in the Netherlands. - EnergyMeasures
38	Inspiration session: Engaging stakeholders in the Netherlands - EnergyMeasures
39	Tips & tricks for saving energy and reducing your energy consumption bills - EnergyMeasures
40	"The outcomes will be more money in households, warmer homes, greater energy efficiency and reduction in emissions." - EnergyMeasures
41	Could you unmute yourself, please? - EnergyMeasures
42	New project to support energy vulnerable households - EnergyMeasures

3.4 Social Media (e.g. Twitter, FB, Instagram)

Method	Stakeholder Group	Indicated KPI	Status (as of 16/02/24)
Social media, e.g. Twitter, FB, Instagram	All stakeholders	600 followers	594 followers on Twitter, FB, Instagram

At the start of EnergyMeasures, a total of three social media channels were set up: Twitter/X, Instagram and Facebook. New and target group-orientated content was continuously produced for the EnergyMeasures channels on Twitter/X and Instagram. Facebook was used with the content created for Instagram, but was never really able to reach a critical audience, partly due to its audience structure and the gradual regionalisation of the networks over the years. In addition to the aforementioned channels, videos, in particular the EnergyMeasures documentary and the recording of the closing event, were hosted on YouTube. In order to achieve visibility without having to build up an audience for an independent channel in the short term, the existing OIKOPLUS channel was used for this purpose.

The [@NRGMeasures on Twitter/X](#) was jointly operated by Oikoplus and UCC. As of 16 February 2024, the channel had **469 followers**. A total of 1,035 posts were made during the project years. In addition to reporting on the day-to-day running of the project, the content shared included information on current blog posts and project outcomes. Two campaigns focussing on 'Energy poverty in Europe' and 'Energy-saving measures' were also shared via Twitter/X

The [EnergyMeasures channel on Instagram](#) was run by OIKOPLUS single-handedly. The channel had a total of **110 followers** on 16 February 2024. A total of 122 static posts and reels were shared on the channel, as well as stories on the topics 'ABOUT', 'WHO', 'HOW', 'CHALLENGES', 'BENEFITS', 'GA Kraków' and 'Brussels Event'. In several campaigns, energy-saving tips, video outtakes of interviews with experts from the project and background information on energy poverty were published.

The EnergyMeasures Facebook channel only has **15 followers**. As already mentioned, no independent materials have been developed for the channel.

The two videos '[Panel Discussion: How to Fight Energy Poverty in Europe](#)' (19 views until 16 February 2024) and '[EnergyMeasures - Tailored measures supporting energy vulnerable households](#)' (90 views until 16 February 2024) were shared on the [OIKOPLUS YouTube channel](#).

In addition to the project's own channels, the EnergyMeasures project was advertised on the partner institutions' own channels (in the local language) in accordance with their guidelines and capacities. In total, over 16,193 people were reached in this way.

3.5 Energy Measures Newsletter

Method	Stakeholder Group	Indicated KPI	Status (as of 16/02/24)
Newsletter	All stakeholders	500 readers	1,464 recipients

A total of five newsletters were produced over the course of the project (December 2021, August 2022, December 2022, May 2023, February 2024). All newsletters are available for download on the website and were also advertised on the social channels of the project and the partner institutions. Due to the many number of options for accessing the newsletters, it is therefore not possible to make a comprehensive list of actual readers. Instead of 'readers', it is instead more reliable only to refer to the 'recipients' of the newsletter.

The recipients are calculated as followers of the social media channels (594 recipients), as well as from the recipients attributed and documented as part of the distribution of the newsletter on the partner organisations' channels. Specific figures for newsletter distribution via the partner organisations' networks are available for Stowarzyszenie Gmin Polska Siéc Energie Cités (139 recipients), Habidom (30 recipients), EnEffect and EcoEnergy (660 recipients), and Oikoplus (41 recipients). In total, the newsletter should have been received by at least 1,464 people per issue.

3.6 Project Leaflets (no KPI mentioned)

In response to demand from partners, OIKOPLUS designed several project flyers in the first half of the project, particularly for recruiting households (see D.6.6.). A total of 28,900 flyers and leaflets were distributed in this context.

In addition to the leaflets, the partner Tigheab Innse Gall arranged for a paid advertisement to be placed in the Outer Hebrides Spotlight magazine for a total of 16 issues with a circulation of 9,000 copies each. The partner Stowarzyszenie Gmin Polska Siéc Energie Cités printed 60 posters which were mainly displayed in schools in the Bielsko-Biala region.

3.7 Project workshops and seminars

Method	Stakeholder Group	Indicated KPI	Status (as of 16/02/24)
Project workshops and seminars	Energy poverty practitioners	200 attendees cumulative	917 attendees cumulative + 386 attendees at training workshops

A total of 29 documented workshops and seminars were organised by the partners during the course of the project. Some of the workshops and seminars were held in online formats due to health regulations, which particularly affected the first half of the project term. The target groups of the workshops and seminars varied depending on the thematic focus. However, three specific contents/target groups can be distinguished: 1) those affected, who were to be informed about their energy consumption and possible measures, 2) decision-makers, who were to be informed about the long-term consequences and costs of energy poverty and about possibilities for structural changes, and 3) local energy experts and advisors, who were to be informed about the opportunities for behavioural change approaches. In total, over 917 people were reached through workshops and seminars (webinars).

In addition to the general project workshops and seminars (webinars), a total of nine training workshops for energy poverty advisers were organised, some of which were internal. These events all took place between March 2021 and September 2023 and were designed to ensure that the people communicating with households as part of EnergyMeasures understood and applied the methodology proposed by EnergyMeasures. In total, over 386 energy poverty advisers took part in the training workshops.

3.8 Paper presentations at scientific conferences

Method	Stakeholder Group	Indicated KPI	Status (as of 16/02/24)
Paper presentations at scientific conferences	Academics and researchers	10 presentations at conferences	2 conference panels convened. 7 conference presentations and 3 guest lectures at universities

EnergyMeasures has been present at several academic conferences over the years. The key partner in terms of academic dissemination was UCC. Under the guise of EnergyMeasures, they convened two panels on energy poverty at the Development Studies Conference 2022, gave a poster presentation at the ERSS Conference 2022 and presented a paper at the Conference of Irish Geographers (Limerick 2022), a paper at the Collective Social Futures Festival of Social Science (Cork 2023), a paper at the ERI Seminar Series (Cork, 2023) and two invited papers as part of the Hunt Museum Culture and Climate Action Seminar Series (Limerick 2023). In addition, Duneworks presented a paper on the EnergyMeasures project at the DRIFT Conference in Rotterdam 2023, as well as a guest lecture at the University of Delft. Het PON & Telos organised two presentations as guest lecturers at TU Eindhoven.

3.9 OA Publications in peer-reviewed journals

Method	Stakeholder Group	Indicated KPI	Status (as of 16/02/24)
OA publications in peer-reviewed journals	Academics and researchers	5 manuscripts	4 OA publications; 1 edited volume; 1 published report

Contrary to the original idea of several individual publications from the project, the university partners decided to publish an anthology entitled "[Living with Energy Poverty - Perspectives from the Global North and South](#)" (see Del. 6.5) after organising two panels at the Development Studies Conference 2022. This anthology contains a total of four contributions on the topic by authors from the consortium, as well as over 18 further contributions by internationally recognised experts on the topic of energy poverty in Europe and beyond. The book is published by Routledge Taylor & Francis Group.

- Velasco-Herrejón, P., Lennon B. & Dunphy, N.P. (Eds) (2023). *Living with Energy Poverty Perspectives from the Global North and South*. London: Routledge
- Velasco-Herrejón, P., Lennon B. & Dunphy, N.P. (2023). The Global Face of Energy Poverty. In: *Living with Energy Poverty Perspectives from the Global North and South*. London: Routledge
- Dunphy, N.P., Lennon B. & Velasco-Herrejón, P. (2023). Identifying Energy-Poor Households, Experiences from the Global North. In: *Living with Energy Poverty Perspectives from the Global North and South*. London: Routledge
- Dunphy, N.P., Lennon B. & Velasco-Herrejón, P. (2023). Towards a better understanding of energy poverty. In: *Living with Energy Poverty Perspectives from the Global North and South*. London: Routledge
- Lennon, B., & Dunphy, N.P. (2024). Sustaining energetic communities: energy citizenship and participation in an age of upheaval and transition. *Scientific Reports*, 14(1), 3267.
- Hesselman, M., Tirado-Herrero, S., Smith, M., ..., Lennon, B., ..., Živčić, L. (2022) Moving forward on the right to energy in the EU. Engagement Toolkit. European Energy Poverty Agenda Co Creation and Knowledge Innovation (ENGAGER), University of Bristol.

To ensure that the project results are available to the community beyond the scientific publications, all deliverables that can be classified as grey literature in science were published on the [EnergyMeasures Zenodo Community](#).

3.10 Cross-participation in events

Method	Stakeholder Group	Indicated KPI	Status (as of 16/02/24)
Cross-participation in events	Cognate projects	10 events (with at least 4 different projects)	10 events (with 8 different projects)

Energy poverty is a topic that is not only addressed by EnergyMeasures. Accordingly, measures were taken as part of the project to establish the project in the professional network. One of the corresponding measures was participation in various events organised by third parties. Two partners or a group of partners and one partner stood out in the network: Gemeente Eindhoven together with Duneworks, HetPON & Telos and Stowarzyszenie Gmin Polska Siéc Energie Cités. In addition to a joint event in which EnEffect and OIKOPLUS participated on behalf of EnergyMeasures, the aforementioned partners presented the project at a total of eight events. The events at which EnergyMeasures was presented were organised by the following projects: [Werkplaats Financien](#), [Energiebox Plus](#), [Groene Wijk Weken](#), [Festiwal Dobrej Energii](#), [S3UNICA](#), [CoM East](#), [LifeTandems](#). The form of participation varied depending on the event - in most cases, however, the project was presented as part of a short presentation.

3.11 Joint events and initiatives

Method	Stakeholder Group	Indicated KPI	Status (as of 16/02/24)
Joint events and initiatives	Cognate projects	3 joint events (with at least 3 different projects)	3 joint events (with 4 different projects)

Three further events were jointly realised as part of EnergyMeasures with a total of four other projects external to the project.

1. "Joint energy advisors training" together with ComAct on 27.07.2021. EnergyMeasures was represented by EnEffect.
2. "Online Conference Addressing Energy Poverty" together with ENPOR on 19.01.2023. EnergyMeasures was represented by Gemeente Eindhoven together with Duneworks, HetPON & Telos.
3. "National Roundtable for financing energy efficiency and RES projects" together with DeSMART and SMAFIN from 16 to 17 March 2022, as well as recurring on 1 March 2023. EnergyMeasures was represented by EcoEnergy.

3.12 Participation in activities of key platforms

Method	Stakeholder Group	Indicated KPI	Status (as of 16/02/24)
Participation in activities of key platforms e.g. Engager Cost Action, EPAH	European Platforms	7 events	6 events

The balance is also positive with regard to the events at which EnergyMeasures was present as part of overarching core platforms. Events and participation in lunch talks and similar events were organised in the context of the [EPAH - European Poverty Advisory Hub Conference](#), EEPF End EnergyPoverty Forum, and the [EUSEW - European Sustainable Energy Week](#) (see D. 6.7). Additionally, the project applied for participation in the European Sustainable Energy Days 2021 but was not selected.

3.13 National Policy Briefings

Method	Stakeholder Group	Indicated KPI	Status (as of 16/02/24)
National Policy Briefings	Policy makers & EU institutions	7+30 attendees	10 events; 428 attendees cumulative

EnergyMeasures produced policy recommendations that were passed on at a total of 10 events and events and policymakers or personnel responsible for energy agendas in the municipalities. A total of 428 people were reached at the events held in the Netherlands, Poland, Ireland and Bulgaria. In six out of ten events, more than 30 people were reached.

3.14 Final project workshop

Method	Stakeholder Group	Indicated KPI	Status (as of 16/02/24)
Final project workshop	Policy makers & EU institutions	50 attendees	33 registrations, 17 attendees, 22 views online.

The final EnergyMeasures event took place on 17 January 2024 at Atelier29 in Brussels. Details on the programme of the event, as well as the invitation policy and follow-up of the event, are explained in detail in D6.7. While there had been promising registrations and good informal confirmations, attendance at the event was substantially frustrated by extreme weather. A severe snowstorm accompanied by an official warning across the city and traffic mayhem resulted in a far lower turnout than expected. Nevertheless 17 people braved the blizzard to attend in person. In addition, the workshop discussion was recorded and made available on YouTube.

4 Conclusion

The final report on the communication and dissemination measures shows that, even if the self-established communications indicators were largely met, some individual formats were found to work better than others. Three aspects will be discussed in more detail below.

1. Audience development and addressing households. While the audience development for Twitter/X and Instagram worked extremely well, the audience development on Facebook, the most regional of the platforms in terms of the use of languages was not as successful. The deficit in audience development, which could have contributed to household participation, was compensated for by extensive flyers and a strong presence in the local media. Both of these communication channels were not initially planned to be used in this form at the start of the project but turned out to be extremely helpful.
2. Workshop formats. With the exception of the final event in Brussels, for which uncontrollable events had a significant negative impact on our efforts in achieving the indicator, all workshop formats, events and seminars exceeded the KPIs. However, the overview of the events also shows that these cannot always be defined as clearly as hoped from the start of the project. Much depends on local needs and interests, but also on how well established the partners are in the region.
3. Science, beyond OA papers. The report also makes it clear that in addition to OA publications and conference papers, there are other formats in which dissemination in academic contexts can succeed. These possibilities include, for example, guest lectures and other activities at universities, but also the organisation of panels and resulting collective publications. It should also be noted to attach particular importance to the publication of grey literature; the most frequently downloaded deliverable from the EnergyMeasures Zenodo repository is D1.1 'Review of Methods of Identifying Energy-Poor Households' - a document that obviously contributes to the formation of definitions in this particularly sensitive area.

In conclusion, it can be stated that the communication indicators themselves represented an incentive to reach as many people as possible. At the same time, however, the report also makes it clear that over the course of the project, the expertise and habits of the project partners contributed to whether indicators can be achieved or whether, as in the case of social media followership for recruiting households, alternatives must be sought in order to supplement unachievable indicators with meaningful alternatives.